

Kinetics and Mechanism of Catalytic Oxidation of Crotonaldehyde to Maleic Anhydride

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The kinetic and mechanistic study of the catalytic oxidation of crotonaldehyde to maleic anhydride has been studied, using molybdenum promoted catalysts. The apparent activation energy for reaction, was found to be 5-3 Kcal/mol. The reaction seems to take place between adsorbed oxygen and adsorbed crotonaldehyde as the rate of reaction was found to be dependent on the partial pressure of the latter. The products do not seem to have any appreciable influence on the kinetics of the oxidative reaction. The rate-equation for the reaction has been given.

Maleic acid and anhydride find wide application in various important industries like plastics, alkyde resins, textiles and leather. In view of their high reactivity, the possibility of finding new and novel uses in the domain of chemical synthesis is almost unlimited. Hitherto the production of maleic acid was chiefly from the oxidation of benzene following the given reaction pattern—

Since this process does not utilize all the carbon atoms and also, considering the importance of benzene in the preparation of various other organic chemicals, it was thought worthwhile by various workers to look for other starting materials having 4 carbon atoms. Notable contributions in this direction are from Hartig¹. He got appreciable yield of maleic anhydride from *n*-butane. The utilization of 1, 3-butadiene for the manufacture of maleic acid has also been reported² and patents have been obtained.

Besides a few patents,^{3a,b,c} the catalytic oxidation of crotonaldehyde has not been investigated in any great detail. The first published work is of Faith and Schaible⁴, who have reported a maximum conversion of 42.2 per cent of crotonaldehyde to maleic acid in presence of V₂O₅—Al₂O₃ granule catalyst, the air-aldehyde ratio being 300. In recent years, Bhattacharya⁵⁻⁶ and his associates published two papers concerning the production of maleic acid from crotonaldehyde using both fixed as well as fluidised beds. More recently Church and Bitha⁷, by using water diluted crotonaldehyde feed, have obtained as high as 80% conversion of crotonaldehyde to maleic acid, V₂O₅ on alumina being the catalyst.

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So far as the oxidation of crotonaldehyde is concerned, it may gathered from the above, that attempts have been made to improve the process efficiency. But any research on process development should further be complemented with kinetic studies in order to promote the process to the commercial level. Though kinetic and mechanistic work on the oxidation of some organic compounds has been done, yet no extensive work has been done on crotonaldehyde. With this idea in view, an investigation on the kinetics and mechanism of the catalytic vapour phase oxidation was undertaken, using $V_2O_5 : MoO_3 : Kg$ (kieselguhr), the catalyst reported by Bhattacharya and his co-workers⁵⁻⁶ as being the best for the purpose. The operating parameters have been varied within a wide range of values with a view of arriving at a general kinetic formulation.

Fig 1. Effect of temp. and S. V. conversion ($V_2O_5 : MoO_3 : Kg$)

The role of V_2O_5 catalysts (promoted and unpromoted) in oxidation reactions deserves careful study, hence three V_2O_5 catalysts two promoted respectively, with titanium oxide and molybdenum oxide and the other being unpromoted have been used in present investigation. An attempt has been made to interpret their catalytic efficiencies in the light of current theories of semiconductor-catalysis.

EXPERIMENTAL

A flow reactor operating at atmospheric pressure, was used. The experimental assembly and the arrangement for feeding the reactants are respectively, similar to ones used by Pandao⁸ and Griffith⁹ *et al.* The reactant, crotonaldehyde was fed to the reactor by mercury displacement. For each run of the experiment 1 g. of catalyst was taken, unless otherwise mentioned.

Analysis of the Products : The product stream contains maleic anhydride unconverted crotonaldehyde and carbon dioxide. Standard procedures have been adopted for the analysis of the above products.

The amount of acid was estimated by titrating the solution with standard alkali and the absence of crotonic acid, a possible product along with maleic acid was confirmed by the methods, outlined by Milas¹⁰, and Church⁷ *et al.* Bromate-bromide reagent added to crotonaldehyde sample was titrated for liberated iodine by sodium thiosulphate solution. This gave the value of unconverted crotonaldehyde¹¹.

The carbon dioxide absorbed in alkali solution and its content was calculated by the difference in alkali before and after the absorption of the gas.

Catalysts : The preparation of catalyst was done according to method followed by Bhattacharya and his co-workers⁵.

Fig 2. Effect of temp. and S. V. on conversion (V₂O₅ : TiO₂O₅ : kg)

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

It has been reported by earlier investigators¹² that crotonaldehyde undergoes thermal polymerisation at elevated temperatures. Hence a few experiments were conducted by passing pure crotonaldehyde through a bed of $V_2O_5 : MoO_3 : Kg$ catalyst at temperatures varying from 350° – 425° and also at different contact times. By analysing the gas and liquid condensate, some 10–15% of crotonaldehyde was found to be lost by forming complex polymerised products. Polymerisation was enhanced with increased temperature and contact time. Even during the purification of feed crotonaldehyde by simple distillation, some 5–10% loss of the aldehyde was noticed.

Due to possible simultaneous polymerisation, a complete material balance could not be obtained for the catalytic vapour phase oxidation of crotonaldehyde. Hence, in the present investigation, the total conversion means the sum of conversions to maleic anhydride (MAA) and carbon dioxide (CO_2), the two oxidation products.

Comparative study of the catalysts in terms of their energy of activation for reaction.

The choice between the following three catalysts was made so as to use them for the kinetic and mechanistic study :

1. $V_2O_5 : MoO_3 : Kg :: 38.9 : 6.8 : 100$
2. $V_2O_5 : TiO_2 : Kg :: 38.9 : 2.3 : 100$
3. $V_2O_5 : Kg :: 50.8 : 100$

Fig 3. Effect of temp. and S. V. on conversion ($V_2O_5 : Kg$)

A comparative study on the performance of these catalysts, was made at 350°, 375°, 400° and 425° at various contact times, maintaining the air-aldehyde ratio and catalyst volume constant. The results are shown in Figs. 1, 2 and 3. During the entire investigation activity was checked periodically to be sure of a steady catalytic activity level. The apparent activation energy for each catalyst was determined by plotting the logarithms of initial rates against the reciprocal of the absolute temperature ($r = Ae^{-E/RT}$). Initial rates were calculated from the slope of the conversion-contact time curves at zero contact time. The values of the apparent activation energy for the different catalysts are as follows :

Catalyst	E_a , Kcals/mole
1. $V_2O_5 : MoO_3 : Kg$	5.3
2. $V_2O_5 : TiO_2 : Kg$	9.3
3. $V_2O_5 : Kg$	5.8

It can be inferred from the above that the incorporation of hexavalent metal like Mo (in the form of oxide) decreases the activation energy for the reaction while the addition of tetravalent titanium, increases it. This is quite expected because the donor impurity (Mo) increases the electron availability at the surface and thus their presence favours the adsorption of oxygen which is supposed to be generally the rate controlling step in oxidation reaction. Butler and Weston¹³ have tried to explain the influence of impurities on the activity of V_2O_5 from the stand-point of phase composition of V_2O_5 lattice and have concluded that tetravalent impurities like titanium oxide not only lowers the availability of electrons to the surface but also may destroy the active centres for oxidation.

Also, it may be concluded from the Arrhenius plots presented in Fig. 4, for the catalysts that the molybdenum promoted vanadium catalyst may possess the highest activity and hence it was selected for the purpose of kinetic and mechanistic studies.

Fig. 4

*Kinetic and Mechanistic Studies—V₂O₅ : MoO₃ : Kg Catalyst.**Studies on Diffusional resistance*

With a view to finding out (i) the minimum feed rate of the reactants and (ii) limiting particle size of the solid catalyst, where resistances of both internal and external diffusion become negligible, two sets of experiments were carried out, varying the particle size of the catalyst in one and in the other the weight size of the catalyst (i.e. reactor volume) being changed. The results obtained with varying size as well as with volume of catalyst have shown that conversion became constant for $-20+25$ mesh size and 1.5 gm of catalyst (3.7 ml volume). Otherwise with more weight and finer size of catalyst both diffusional resistance and polymerisation were taking place, thus affecting the conversion.

Keeping these points in view, all further studies were made at 400° with a contact time of 0.018 sec and 1 g. of catalyst.

Variation of partial pressure

(a) *Crotonaldehyde* : The effect of partial pressure of crotonaldehyde was studied by changing the feed rate of crotonaldehyde and keeping the rate of air flow constant. Fig. 5 shows that with the increase in the partial pressure of aldehyde the rate, total (maleic anhydride + CO₂) as well as for maleic anhydride alone, increased to attain maximum and again fell.

(b) *Oxygen* : The effect of partial pressure of oxygen on conversion rates were studied by mixing the incoming air with nitrogen or when necessary with pure oxygen. However for fear of explosion and the exothermic nature of the reaction at higher oxygen concentration, the partial pressure of oxygen was varied upto 0.35 atm. The experiments were conducted at a constant contact time and gas-aldehyde ratio. Fig. 6 shows that with the increase in partial pressure of oxygen within the range studied, the rate of total conversion as well as for maleic anhydride increased gradually to attain the study values. They might have shown a decline, had higher partial pressure of oxygen been used but due to reasons given above higher partial pressures could not be used.

(c) *Both crotonaldehyde and oxygen* : This aspect was studied under the constant feed of total gas, keeping the aldehyde-oxygen ratio constant. It was found that the rate increases linearly with oxygen partial pressure up to a value of 0.12 atm and with higher oxygen partial pressure it tends to a steady value.

(d) *Carbon dioxide* : Varying amounts of carbon dioxide, comparable to the usual amounts produced by the reaction, were mixed along with air to change the partial pressure of carbon dioxide. Figure 7 shows that carbon dioxide does not affect the conversion to any appreciable extent. Hence it was concluded that the incorporation of CO₂ affected only the equilibrium of the reaction and that too very little.

(e) *Effect of maleic anhydride* : Incorporation of maleic anhydride, the main product in the feed brought about considerable polymerisation of crotonaldehyde as indicated by wide difference in material balance calculations. Due to this, the conversion to maleic anhydride suffered a drastic decline. The conversion to maleic anhydride was lowered

from 7.2% to 2.4% by increasing the maleic anhydride feed from 0 to 4.5 gm/100 ml in the feed, the conversion fell one-third of the original value.

Fig. 5

This way of expressing the conversion on the basis of total aldehyde fed does not give the true picture, since, under the conditions, a major portion of the aldehyde is not available for oxidation. But if the conversion to maleic anhydride is calculated on the basis of total oxidative conversion, the effect of polymerisation could be viewed as not much, 69.3 to 53.5% (Table 1).

TABLE I

Amount of MAA in 100 ml Croton.	% Recovery MAA in Train	% Conversion		Unconverted Croton.	Actual MAA	Actual % of MAA
		MAA	CO ₂			
0.0	0.0	7.2	3.2	76.3	0.0	69.3
1.2	1.0	5.1	1.9	68.7	4.1	68.5
4.5	3.6	6.0	2.0	67.7	2.4	54.5
4.5	3.6	5.9	2.0	62.2	2.3	53.5
0.0	0.0	6.9	3.2	73.8	0.0	68.3

(Effect of maleic anhydride on the conversion of crotonaldehyde to maleic anhydride).

The effect of water : The influence of another product, water, was also studied and it was found that their presence could not affect the conversion much. The results are given below :

Amount of water in gms.	Moles % aldehyde converted	
	MAA	CO ₂
0.00	7.6	2.8
0.90	7.8	3.7
1.85	7.3	4.6
2.60	7.2	4.6

Discussion and rate equation : The following general conclusions may be drawn from the foregoing studies on the transport resistance and also on the influence of the partial pressure of the reactants and products :

(i) Diffusional process may be considered to be offering negligible resistance under the condition of the experiments.

(ii) The fact that the oxidation rates both for total and for maleic anhydride conversion passed through a maximum with increase in the partial pressure of crotonaldehyde suggests that the reaction takes place between the adsorbed oxygen and crotonaldehyde¹⁴. The maxima in the rate Vs P_{O_2} curve are absent since higher values of P_{O_2} could not be used for reasons of explosion and enhanced exothermic nature of reaction.

Fig. 6

(iii) The adsorption of products does not seem to have any appreciable influence on the kinetics of the oxidative reaction. Had any of the desorption steps been the controlling steps, the rates of reaction would have been dependent on them.

(iv) Under the present experimental conditions, air/aldehyde ratio was always kept at a very high value. Hence the effect of P_{O_2} at constant air/aldehyde ratio may well be looked upon as the effect of total pressure on the rates, assuming of course that under steady state, nitrogen, an inert, does not affect the rate to any extent. The nature of the curve in Fig. 5, indicates that the chemisorption of oxygen is the rate controlling step. This conclusion seems to be logical and in agreement with the observations made by a number of other workers, mentioned earlier in the paper.

On the above conclusion, the following are the postulated mechanisms :

Mechanism—1

Reaction between adsorbed molecular oxygen and adsorbed crotonaldehyde (dual site mechanism), adsorption of oxygen being the rate controlling step.

The derived rate equation is given by the relation—

$$** \quad \frac{P_{O_2}}{r} = \alpha + \beta \frac{P_{MAA}}{P_{Crot}} + \gamma P_{Crot}$$

Mechanism—2

Reaction between atomically adsorbed oxygen and adsorbed crotonaldehyde, adsorption of oxygen is the rate controlling step.

The equation being—

$$** \quad \sqrt{\frac{P_{O_2}}{r}} = \alpha + \beta - \frac{P_{MAA}}{P_{Crot}} + \gamma P_{Crot}$$

Consideration of other mechanisms like the reaction between adsorbed oxygen and gaseous crotonaldehyde becomes inconsistent in the light of the dependence of reaction rate on the partial pressure of crotonaldehyde.

Fig. 7 Effect of CO_2 on MAA conversion ($V_2O_5 : M_0O_3 : Kg$)

The validity of the above rate equations is tested in the light of the experimental results. The values of constants α , β and γ of suggested rate equations were calculated by the method of least square using the experimental values of partial pressure for oxygen, crotonaldehyde and maleic anhydride. The results thus obtained are

**Where P_{O_2} , P_{MAA} , and P_{Crot} are respective partial pressures of oxygen, maleic anhydride and crotonaldehyde; r , the rate; α , β and γ are constants.

summarised below.

The values of constants for different mechanisms.

Equation	Value of constant	Remarks	Calculated rates		Experimental rates*	
			Total	MAA		
i) $\frac{P_{O_2}}{r} = + \frac{P_{MAA}}{P_{Crot}} + P_{Crot}$	$\alpha = 1.3$	The values of constants are positive and theoretical curve fits nicely with the experimental one.	3.50	3.00	2.50	2.17
	$\beta = 525.0$		4.40	3.68	3.78	3.24
	$\gamma = 1127.0$		7.30	4.00	7.88	4.25
	—		—	—	—	—
	—		7.50	5.30	7.50	5.30
			3.50	—	5.40	4.30
ii) $\sqrt{\frac{P_{O_2}}{r}} = + \frac{P_{MAA}}{P_{Crot}} + P_{Crot}$	$\alpha = 2.50$	The values of the constants are positive and curve is fitting nicely with experimental.				
	$\beta = 52.04$ $\gamma = 107.00$					
					Please refer Figure 5.	

* The rates are expressed gm mole/hour/gm & P_{O_2} constant and P_{Crot} varied.

It is obvious from the above table that both the mechanisms are the acceptable ones. Of these two possible mechanisms, the first one is found to be more reasonable because on separate chemisorption studies of oxygen at constant volume, we found that the equation¹⁵ for atomic adsorption was not obeyed (data to be published). The agreement between experimental data and those calculated indicates that the oxidation of crotonaldehyde takes place through the reaction of adsorbed oxygen and crotonaldehyde.

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